

LARGE-SCALE B, N-CODOPED HIERARCHICALLY NANOPOROUS CARBON NANOFIBERS AS EFFICIENT METAL-FREE CATALYSTS FOR ORR

Yongpeng Lei¹, Qi Shi², Hongling Yuan¹ and Yingde Wang²

¹ College of Basic Education, National University of Defense Technology,
Changsha, 410073, P. R. China

Email: lypkd@163.com (Y.P. Lei), hongliangyuan@126.com (H.L. Yuan)

² Science and Technology on Advanced Ceramic Fiber and Composites Laboratory, National
University of Defense Technology, Changsha, 410073, P. R. China

Email: wyd502@163.com (Y.D. Wang)

Keywords: Electrospun carbon nanofibers, Ammonia, Micro/mesoporous structure, Oxygen reduction reaction

ABSTRACT

B, N-codoped carbon nanofibers were massively prepared by post heat treatment of electrospun carbon nanofibers with the mixture of boric acid/urea in N₂ (BNC_f-N) and subsequently in NH₃ (BNC_f-NA). The microstructure and composition were characterized by SEM, TEM, TGA, XRD, IR and Raman spectroscopy. XPS measurements further show the BNC_f-NA with a composition of 5.25 at% B and 6.68 at% N, especially more B-N-C and pyridinic-N than BNC_f-N, which is beneficial for oxygen reduction reaction (ORR). Nitrogen adsorption experiments exhibit that BNC_f-NA have more micro/mesopores and a high surface area of 306.3 m² g⁻¹. These intriguing features render BNC_f-NA with a comparable performance in reaction current density and ORR peak potential to the commercial Pt/C catalyst. Furthermore, BNC_f-NA illustrate excellent cycling stability, good methanol tolerance and efficient direct four-electron pathway for ORR in alkaline media. Our work provides a large-scale preparation method to generate low-cost, efficient metal-free catalysts for ORR, which would further intensify the commercial application of fuel cells.

1 INTRODUCTION

Oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) has aroused considerable attention due to its significance in fuel cell applications [1,2]. Commercial Pt/C electrocatalysts have been widely used in fuel cells for their comparatively low overpotential and high current density. However, apart from the limited natural reserves and high cost of Pt, the sluggish kinetics, poor stability and anode crossover in electrochemical environments have severely encumbered Pt/C catalysts' extensive applications [3-5]. Thus, based on metal-free materials, the cheap and effective electrocatalysts with comparable ORR activity and higher durability are highly desired.

As known, carbon materials have been widely studied as catalyst and support for electrochemical applications [6,7]. Intensive research efforts are focused on the preparation of metal-free carbon-based ORR catalysts, such as graphene [8,9], carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [10], nanoporous carbon [11,12] and carbon nanosheets [13]. Among them, the partial substitution of carbon atoms with heteroatoms such as N, B, S, P and I, is an effective method to break the electroneutrality and introduce defects to the neighbouring sites, which can donor its electrons to oxygen with ease. Thus it leads to the enhancement of catalytic sites and ORR activity [14]. Compared to single-doped carbon materials, the dual-doped, even tri-doped ones performed much better in activity and durability [15]. For example, B, N-codoped graphene exhibited much improved electrochemical performance as compared to that of single-doped graphene [16]. In this regard, the introduction of two or more heteroatoms into carbon is becoming a main strategy in obtaining efficient carbon-based ORR catalysts.

At the same time, hierarchically porous structure and unique surface composition are also very crucial to the ORR performance. Very recently, Müllen *et al.* [17] found that NH₃ activation could introduce micropores, and most importantly, the employment of NH₃ played a crucial role in attaining an optimal surface functionality of carbon catalysts for ORR.

Lately, self-supported low-dimensional nanostructures for electrocatalytic applications have attracted great attention [18]. Yu and co-authors reported a free-standing porous carbon nanofibers/selenium composite electrode with good flexibility, exhibiting superior electrochemical performance for both Li-ion and Na-ion storage. The 3D interconnected porous carbon nanofibers framework with excellent electronic conductivity facilitated electron and ion transportation and the high porosity promoted ion diffusion in the electrolyte, both of which are important for high power density. Electrospinning is one of the most promising ways to prepare 1D nanomaterials with controllable composition and porous structure in large scale [19-22]. The directly electrospun self-standing 3D non-woven structure was accomplished as a perfect support for catalytically active sites as binder-free electrocatalyst [23]. So, designing porous dual-doped carbon nanofibers is more meaningful and can possibly meet the demands for ORR catalyst.

Lately, we have prepared hierarchically porous SiC ultrafine fibers [24], N-doped TiO₂ nanofibers [25], N-doped TiO₂/C nanofibers [26] and corresponding 3D non-woven webs. It is worthy to note that we designed and fabricated multi-needle electrospinning setup [27]. In the present work, we prepared B, N-codoped CNFs with hierarchically porous structure by heat treatment of electrospun CNFs with the mixture of boric acid/urea in N₂ (BNC_r-N) and then activated in NH₃ (BNC_r-NA). The NH₃ activation here was used to provide the nanofibers more activity sites, high surface area and hierarchically nanoporous structure. Combined with the directly formed void spaces between each fiber, the mass transport of reactant and resulted molecules were improved, leading to a higher utilization rate of electrocatalysts. As expected, the BNC_r-NA show comparable current density and ORR peak potential with nearly four-electron selectivity, while much higher stability and methanol tolerance than that of a commercial Pt/C catalyst.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Preparation of BNC_r-N and BNC_r-NA

The schematic illustration of the scalable fabrication of BNC_r-N and BNC_r-NA is shown in Fig. 1. Polyacrylonitrile (PAN, Japan Kaneka) with an average molecular weight of 9.45×10^4 g mol⁻¹ was dried at 70 °C in air before use. 11 wt% PAN was dissolved thoroughly in N, N-Dimethylformamide (DMF, Shanghai Titanchem Co., Ltd, China). Then they were used to fabricate PAN precursor nanofibers with our self-designed multi-needle electrospinning setup. And the as-obtained green fibers were cured at 250 °C (3 °C min⁻¹, air) for 1 h and then pyrolyzed at 1000 °C for 2 h (3 °C min⁻¹, N₂) to obtain CNFs with diameters between 200 and 300 nm.

Figure 1: Scheme showing the large-scale preparation of B, N-codoped CNFs.

The obtained CNFs (0.2 g) were mixed with a solution of 0.03 g boric acid (Tianjin Hengxing Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd, China) and 0.36 g urea (Taishan Yueqiao Reagent Plastics CO., Ltd, China) in 50 ml deionized water by sonication. Then the mixture was dried in an oven of 120 °C for 7

h. B and N atoms were doped into the CNFs by annealing with the mixture of boric acid/urea under N₂ (900 °C, 3.5 °C min⁻¹, 7 h) and BNC_F-N were received. The relative contents of B and N atoms can be tuned and more nanopores would be introduced by further treated under NH₃ (930 °C, 3 °C min⁻¹, 3 h) and BNC_F-NA were obtained.

2.2 Characterization

The morphology of the fibers was observed using a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM, Hitachi S-4800, Japan). The high-resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM) and selected-area electron diffraction (SAED) were carried out using a JEOL JEM-2100 microscope (Japan). The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were obtained with a powder X-ray diffractometer (Siemens D-5005, CuK_α radiation, Germany). Fourier transformed infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra were recorded on a Nicolet Avatar 360 spectrophotometer (USA) between 400 and 2000 cm⁻¹ as KBr pellets. The Raman spectra were obtained on a LabRAM HR Raman spectrometer (France) using a 488 nm, 50× objective, 1.3 mW laser intensity, air-cooled Ar⁺ laser. The thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA) was operated on a Perkin-Elmer TGA instrument in air with a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectra were obtained using a VG ESCALAB MKII instrument (Al K_α excitation, UK). The specific surface areas (*S*_{BET}) were evaluated by the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method from nitrogen adsorption data recorded with a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 nitrogen adsorption apparatus (USA). And the pore size distributions were calculated by using the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method.

To demonstrate the porous structure of BNC_F-NA, methylene blue (MB) was used to study the adsorption behaviors of as-prepared samples in aqueous solution. 0.1 g sample was added to 100 mL MB solution (10 mg L⁻¹) at room temperature. After every selected time intervals (60 s), ~3.0 mL MB solution was removed out and dynamic MB concentration was investigated by a 722S visible spectrophotometer (INESA Scientific Instrument Co., Ltd.,) at 664 nm. The equilibrium adsorption capacities (*q_e*) are ascertained by the following equation (eq. 1) [24]:

$$q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_e)V}{m} \quad (1)$$

where *V* is the solution volume, *C*₀ and *C*_{*e*} are the original concentration and the residual concentration, respectively, *m* is the mass of the adsorbent.

The electrochemical measurements were conducted on a computer-controlled potentiostat (CHI 660e, Chenhua, China) with a three-electrode electrochemical cell. The glassy carbon electrode (GCE, 7.065 mm²) or rotating disk electrode (RDE-3A, ALS, Japan, 12.56 mm²) loaded with catalyst was served as the working electrode. A Pt wire and Ag/AgCl electrode were used as the counter electrode and the reference electrode, respectively. All the experiments were conducted at room temperature. The CNF based catalysts were transferred onto the GCE or RDE by the following procedures: Firstly, the catalysts were well dispersed in 3:1 v/v water/isopropanol solvent with a concentration of 5 g L⁻¹ by sonication. Then 6 μL and 8 μL catalyst suspension were dropped onto the GCE and RDE, respectively. Lastly, the dry catalyst layer was coated by Nafion solution (0.5 wt%).

The cyclic voltammograms (CVs) of all samples were studied in O₂- and N₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH electrolyte at a scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹. The linear sweep voltammetry curves (LSVs) of all the samples were obtained with a rotating speed of 1600 rpm on a RDE at a scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹. Especially, the BNC_F-NA catalyst was performed on the RDE at different rotating speeds (400, 600, 900, 1200 and 1600 rpm) to understand the ORR mechanism and the primary electrocatalytic process. Methanol was introduced into the 0.1 M KOH electrolyte to examine the methanol crossover resistance by CVs. Durability tests of the BNC_F-NA and the Pt/C electrocatalyst (Pt/C, Pt: 20 wt%, Alfa Aesar, Johnson Matthey) were conducted by the CVs in the O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH up to 1000 cycles. For all the tests carried out in O₂-saturated electrolyte, O₂ was bubbled into the electrolyte to reach O₂ saturation during the test. The same procedure was applied for the test performed in N₂-saturated electrolyte by replacing O₂ with N₂.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first page must contain the Title, Author(s), Affiliation(s), Key words and the Summary. The Introduction must begin immediately below, following the format of this template.

Fig. 2(a) and (b) show the SEM images of BNC_{r-N} and BNC_{r-NA} , respectively. The BNC_{r-N} illustrate homogeneous diameter (~ 300 nm) and smooth surface. However, the obtained BNC_{r-NA} show comparatively rough surface with many nanopores aroused by partial decarbonization. The possible reactions involved in the preparation of BNC_{r-NA} are summarized as follows (eq. 2-6), namely the decomposition of urea (eq. 2), dehydration of H_2BO_3 (eq. 3), formation of BN (eq. 4) and BCN (eq. 5), and partial decarbonization (eq. 6). The released gases involved in the overall reaction caused light exfoliation of CNFs and thus the rough surface formed (Fig. 2(b) and (c)). The introduced nanopores increase the surface area and the number of catalytic sites, which is favorable for ORR. Fig. 2(c) gives the TEM image of BNC_{r-NA} , displaying rough surface and nanoporous structure, corresponding well to the SEM results. The SAED pattern with two diffuse rings arises from the (002) and (100) reflections (inset in Fig. 2(c)), similar to the patterns of graphitic-like materials. The HRTEM result (Fig. 2(d)) confirms the existence of (002) interlayer fringes in small crystalline domains, indicating low crystallinity of BNC_{r-NA} [28].

Figure 2: SEM images of (a) BNC_{r-N} and (b) BNC_{r-NA} , (c) TEM and (d) HRTEM images of BNC_{r-NA} .

To investigate the influence of doping on the CNFs, the XRD patterns for BNC_{r-NA} , BNC_{r-N} and CNFs were measured, as shown in Fig. 3(a). The typical patterns show (002) and (100) broad graphitic peaks at 26° and 43° (2θ), respectively [29,30], pointing out a low degree of crystallization for all the three samples. The result corresponds well with the SAED and HRTEM outcome as given in Fig. 2(c) and Fig. 2(d), respectively. For the FTIR spectra (Fig. 3(b)), the peak at 1383 cm^{-1} is attributed to B-N bond [31,32]. And the absorption bands near 1580 and 1250 cm^{-1} are ascribed to C=N and C-N bonds, respectively. The weak C=N bond in CNFs originates from the transformation of C \equiv N bond during heat treatment [26,33]. As can be seen, the peak intensity of C=N around 1580 cm^{-1} for BNC_{r-NA} is stronger and sharper than those of BNC_{r-N} and CNFs, demonstrating the effective incorporation of N element by activated in NH_3 .

Raman is a useful tool for providing detailed information about the microstructure feature of graphitic-like materials [34]. Fig. 3(c) shows the Raman spectra of the three samples with two obvious peaks. The D band at about 1360 cm^{-1} and G band near 1580 cm^{-1} are ascribed to the disordered and

ordered structure of carbon material, respectively. The band intensity ratio (I_D/I_G) is generally used to measure the carbon disorder, and a higher I_D/I_G value demonstrates more defects in the carbon structure. The I_D/I_G values for the as-prepared CNFs, BNC_{r-N} and BNC_{r-NA} are 2.06, 2.30 and 2.41, respectively. This indicates that both the B, N-codoping and the NH_3 activation increase the defect sites in CNFs, which is favorable for ORR.

The TGA curves in Fig. 3(d) show the weight loss of two samples up to 850 °C in air, mainly due to the oxidization of carbon and BCN (eq. 7) [28]. BNC_{r-NA} have a higher mass loss rate while a greater residual mass than BNC_{r-N} . The faster weight loss can be reasonably attributed to the high surface area of BNC_{r-NA} , which facilitates oxygen diffusion and thus strengthens the oxidation reaction of carbon matrix. However, BNC_{r-NA} have more boron nitride (BN), which can be proved from the FTIR above and the XPS spectra below. The oxidation of BN generally occurs above 900 °C [35], so BNC_{r-NA} have a higher weight retain. In comparison with the homogeneous BCN material [28], the comparatively low mass retention here can be ascribed to the surface doping of CNFs, which introduce comparatively low BCN content.

Figure 3: (a) XRD patterns, (b) FTIR spectra, (c) Raman spectra of CNFs, BNC_{r-N} and BNC_{r-NA} , (d) TGA curves of BNC_{r-N} and BNC_{r-NA} .

To further analyse the doping level and surface functionalities of sample after NH_3 activation, both of the B 1s and N 1s XPS spectra of BNC_{r-N} and BNC_{r-NA} were illustrated in Fig. 4. And Table 1 lists the component and the content of nitrogen functional groups of two samples determined by XPS. The relative content of B and N increased after NH_3 activation, providing more defect sites and potential advantage for electrocatalytic activity. In Fig. 4(a) and (c), after deconvolution of the B1s, the three peaks around 190, 191 and 192 eV can be ascribed to the B-C, B-N and B-O bonds, respectively [29]. As illustrated in Fig. 4(b) and (d), the N1s spectra of both samples are deconvoluted into five N species: graphitic-N (401.3 eV), pyrrolic/pyridone-N (400.7 eV), B-N-C (399.5 eV), pyridinic-N (398.4 eV) and B-N (397.7 eV) [16,36,37]. The content of defect sites is enhanced after NH_3 activation, which agrees well with the Raman results. Among the five N functionalities, graphitic- and pyridinic-N are the most frequently proposed as favourable for ORR [38-40]. Remarkably, the relative amount of pyridinic-N (Table 1) increased from 13 (BNC_{r-N}) to 41% (BNC_{r-NA}) after NH_3 activation, which should show positive effect on ORR performance. It is reported that B-N-C sites may also cause enhanced ORR activity. And the B-N-C sites in BNC_{r-N} and BNC_{r-NA} demonstrate the synergistic effect of the B, N-codoping [36,41]. These results distinctly suggest that the NH_3 activation can dramatically restructures the surface functionalities, which are crucial to enhance the ORR activity.

Figure 4: B 1s and N 1s XPS spectra of (a and b) BNC_f-N and (c and d) BNC_f-NA.

Sample	B	C	N	graphitic-N	pyrrolic/ pyridone-N	B-N-C	pyridinic-N	B-N
BNC _f -N	1.60	87.42	3.40	1.52	0.65	0.43	0.44	0.36
BNC _f -NA	5.25	76.99	6.68	1.30	0.48	0.93	2.73	1.24

Table 1: XPS data of BNC_f-N and BNC_f-NA.

Regarding the ORR activity, it is evident that rich microporosity can provide numerous accessible active sites, while high mesoporosity is beneficial for the quick mass transfer in the catalyst layer [17]. Hence, large S_{BET} and hierarchically porous structure are highly desirable [42]. To analyze the pore structure of the two samples, nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K were carried out (Fig. 5). The isotherms are of type IV with the hysteresis in the desorption branch, showing the existence of mesopores in BNC_f-N and BNC_f-NA. However, at low p/p_0 region ($p/p_0 < 0.1$), BNC_f-NA have rapid adsorption increment, which may be assigned to the presence of micropores [43]. Table 2 gives the nitrogen adsorption data of two samples. As seen, the S_{BET} were calculated to be 24.7 and 306.3 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$, with average pore diameters of 6.1 and 2.4 nm for BNC_f-N and BNC_f-NA, respectively. Obviously, the BNC_f-NA possess a lower average pore diameter. NH_3 activation improves the S_{BET} and introduces more micropores, endowing BNC_f-NA with the micro/mesoporous structure. Thus it greatly promote the mass transport and increase the active sites [44], thereby further enhancing the ORR activity. And it may provide BNC_f-NA with potential applications in hydrogen storage [45]. The NH_3 activation appears to be an effective method to simultaneously introduces more micropores and optimize surface functionality of the doped carbon, both of which are important to enhance the ORR activity.

Figure 5: Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K and pore size distributions (the inset) of (a) BNC_r-N and (b) BNC_r-NA.

Sample	S_{BET} ($\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$)	APD (nm)	V ($\text{mm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$)
BNC _r -N	24.7	6.1	37.8
BNC _r -NA	306.3	2.4	181.0

Table 2 Nitrogen adsorption data of BNC_r-N and BNC_r-NA.

To further illustrate the porous structure and S_{BET} of BNC_r-NA, the adsorption capability was investigated by utilizing MB dye as a model compound. Fig. 6 shows the absorption behavior in MB solution. As seen, BNC_r-NA display 99% adsorption quantity in 4 minutes, while BNC_r-N and CNFs only show 59.5% and 54.6%, respectively. The result indicates that NH₃ activation has a great effect on the porous structure, enabling the rapid mass transport of guest species. Therefore the BNC_r-NA are also of great interest in absorption and catalysis.

Figure 6: The adsorption of MB by CNFs, BNC_r-N and BNC_r-NA.

To have a knowledge of the sample's electrocatalytic performance for ORR, we performed CV measurements in O₂- and N₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution using a conventional three-electrode system. As shown in Fig. 7(a), (b) and (c), in O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution, ORR peaks at -0.60 V, -0.42 V and -0.33 V (vs Ag/AgCl) were observed for CNFs, BNC_r-N and BNC_r-NA, respectively, while those signals did not appear in N₂-saturated solution. The peak potential of BNC_r-NA is about 0.09 and 0.27 V more positive than that of BNC_r-N and CNFs, respectively. The current density of BNC_r-NA is also higher. Apparently, when B and N elements were introduced to CNFs, the activity became much higher. And after NH₃ activation, the activity is further improved, which can be possibly attributed to the more micro/mesopores, enhanced surface area, higher content of B-N-C and pyridinic-N verified by XPS. It is obvious that the peak potential of the commercial Pt/C catalyst for ORR is located at around -0.16V. The durability tests of Pt/C catalyst before and after 1000 CV cycles indicate the weak stability (Fig. 7(d)). However, the ORR peak potential and current density of BNC_r-NA do not manifest any obvious changes, highlighting the electrocatalytic stability during ORR.

Figure 7: Electrochemical performance of (a) CNFs, (b) BNC_r-N, (c) BNC_r-NA and (d) Pt/C.

As known, methanol can penetrate through the proton exchange membrane and oxidize in cathode, which severely deteriorate Pt catalyst and the whole cell performance [46,47]. Thus, methanol was added into electrolyte (the ultimate methanol concentration in 0.1 M KOH is 3 M) to detect the methanol crossover effect. As displayed in Fig. 8(a), the original ORR performance of Pt/C was greatly impacted by the addition of methanol, indicating the prominent oxidation of methanol and the poisoning of catalyst, which would greatly influence the electrocatalytic performance and reduce the service life of fuel cells. It is worth noting that the ORR peak potential and current density of BNC_r-NA remained almost unchanged (Fig. 8(b)). These results suggest that BNC_r-NA are rarely affected by methanol crossover, making them potential alternative catalysts for ORR.

Figure 8: Typical CVs for (a) the Pt/C and (b) the BNC_r-NA in an O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution or an O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution upon addition of CH₃OH. Scan rate: 100 mV s⁻¹.

As shown in Figure 9 (a), for further insight into the electrocatalytic performance of the BNC_r-NA during the ORR process, we compared their linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) with CNFs, BNC_r-NA and commercial Pt/C using a rotating disk electrode (RDE). The LSV measurements were performed in an O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution with the same loading of 0.32 mg cm⁻². Fig. 9(a) demonstrates that the ORR onset potential on BNC_r-NA electrode (at -0.068 V) was more positive than those of CNFs and BNC_r-N, and the value is slightly inferior to that of Pt/C (at -0.008 V). The more positive ORR onset potential of BNC_r-NA indicates a more accessible ORR process.

Figure 9: (a) RDE voltammograms of the CNFs, BNC_r-N, BNC_r-NA, and Pt/C obtained at a rotation rate of 1600 rpm. Scan rate: 10 mV s⁻¹. (b) The transferred electron number (n) and RDE voltammograms (inset) of the BNC_r-NA obtained at different rotation rates. (c) The corresponding Koutecky–Levich plots of BNC_r-NA. (d) The transferred electron number (n) and RDE voltammograms (inset) of Pt/C.

As shown below, the four-electron reduction pathway (eq. 8) is highly desired in fuel cell systems. However, the two-electron reduction pathway (eq. 9) leading to hydrogen peroxide is unwanted because it is a main reason for the chemically degraded membrane and catalysts [48]. To gain an understanding of the electron transfer parameters of the BNC_r-NA catalyst, we performed the RDE experiments of BNC_r-NA and Pt/C at different rotating speeds (Fig. 9(b) (inset) and Fig. 9(d) (inset)). Fig. 9(c) is the Koutecky-Levich plots of BNC_r-NA. Koutecky-Levich equation (eq. 10 and eq. 11) relating the current density to the rotation rate of the electrode, was used to calculate the electron transfer number (n) per oxygen molecule. It is worth noting that the obtained transferred electron number of BNC_r-NA is 3.43–3.86 ranging from -0.5 to -0.9 V (Fig. 9 (b)), showing the preferable selectivity for the efficient four-electron ORR pathway. For comparison, the calculated n of Pt/C is nearly 4 in the range from -0.4 to -0.7 V (Fig. 9 (d)). All these results suggest that the BNC_r-NA show better ORR catalytic performance. It is necessary to point out that, thanks to the synergetic effect of B, N-codoping, large S_{BET} , unique micro/mesoporous structure and directly formed void spaces during electrospinning, the large scaled BNC_r-NA could be potential alternative catalyst for ORR.

$$\frac{1}{j} = \frac{1}{j_k} + \frac{1}{B\omega^{0.5}} \quad (10)$$

$$B = 0.2nF(D_{\text{O}_2})^{2/3} \nu^{-1/6} C_{\text{O}_2} \quad (11)$$

4 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we have revealed a facile way to prepare micro/mesoporous B, N-codoped 3D micro-mesoporous CNFs web in large scale. Compared with carbon supported commercial Pt/C catalysts, the

3D BNC_r-NA web shows high electrocatalytic efficiency, much better stability and methanol tolerance, appearing to be one of the potential candidates for cost-effective metal-free ORR electrocatalyst. The NH₃ activation appears to be valid for simultaneously introducing more micropores and optimizing surface functionality of the doped carbon. The enhanced ORR performance is mainly ascribed to the synergetic effect of the optimized B, N codoping and surface functionality, high surface area and hierarchically nanoporous structure. The directly formed void spaces during electrospinning also play an important role. Moreover, the BNC_r-NA could be employed in energy and environment related fields such as supercapacitor, hydrogen storage, purification of contaminated water and so on.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was financially supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (51203182, 51173202), Hunan Provincial Natural Science Foundation of China (13JJ4009), Open Research Fund Program of the State Key Laboratory of Low-Dimensional Quantum Physics (KF201312), The State Key Laboratory of Refractories and Metallurgy (Wuhan University of Science and Technology), State Key Laboratory for Mechanical Behavior of Materials, Xi'an Jiaotong University (20131304), Key Laboratory of High Performance fibers & products, Ministry of Education, Donghua University.

REFERENCES

- [1] X.P. Gao, H.X. Yang, Multi-electron reaction materials for high energy density batteries. *Energy Environ. Sci.*, **3**, 2010, pp. 174-189.
- [2] Y.M. Liu, S. Chen, X. Quan, H.T. Yu, H.M. Zhao, Y.B. Zhang, G.H. Chen, Boron and nitrogen codoped nanodiamond as an efficient metal-free catalyst for oxygen reduction reaction, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, **117**, 2013, pp. 14992-14998.
- [3] Y. Liang, Y. Li, H. Wang, J. Zhou, J. Wang, T. Regier, H. Dai, Co₃O₄ nanocrystals on graphene as a synergistic catalyst for oxygen reduction reaction, *Nat. Mater.*, **10**, 2011, pp. 780-786.
- [4] K.P. Gong, F. Du, Z.H. Xia, M. Durstock, L.M. Dai, Nitrogen-doped carbon nanotube arrays with high electrocatalytic activity for oxygen reduction, *Science*, **323**, 2009, pp. 760-764.
- [5] S. Chu, A. Majumdar, Opportunities and challenges for a sustainable energy future, *Nature*, **488**, 2012, pp. 294-303.
- [6] K.N. Wood, R. O'Hayre, S. Pylypenko, Recent progress on nitrogen/carbon structures designed for use in energy and sustainability applications, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, **7**, 2014, pp. 1212-1249.
- [7] A. Nouralishahi, A. M. Rashidi, Y. Mortazavi, A. Ali Khodadadi, M. Choolaei, Enhanced methanol electro-oxidation reaction on Pt-CoO_x/MWCNTs hybrid electro-catalyst, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, **335**, 2015, pp. 55-64.
- [8] S. Yang, L. Zhi, K. Tang, X. Feng, J. Maier, K. Müllen, Efficient synthesis of heteroatom (N or S)-doped graphene based on ultrathin graphene oxide-porous silica sheets for oxygen reduction reactions, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **22**, 2012, pp. 3634-3640.
- [9] S. Wang, L. Zhang, Z. Xia, A. Roy, D.W. Chang, J.B. Baek, L.M. Dai, BCN graphene as efficient metal-free electrocatalyst for the oxygen reduction reaction, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **51**, 2012, pp. 4209-4212.
- [10] S.Y. Wang, E. Iyyamperumal, A. Roy, Y.H. Xue, D.S. Yu, L.M. Dai, Vertically aligned BCN nanotubes as efficient metal-free electrocatalysts for the oxygen reduction reaction: a synergetic effect by co-doping with boron and nitrogen, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **50**, 2011, pp. 11756-11760.
- [11] Z. Liu, G. Zhang, Z. Lu, X. Jin, Z. Chang, X. Sun, One-step scalable preparation of N-doped nanoporous carbon as a high-performance electrocatalyst for the oxygen reduction reaction, *Nano Res.*, **6**, 2013, pp. 293-301.
- [12] D.S. Yang, D. Bhattacharjya, S. Inamdar, J. Park, J.S. Yu, Phosphorus-doped ordered mesoporous carbons with different lengths as efficient metal-free electrocatalysts for oxygen reduction reaction in alkaline media, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **134**, 2012, pp. 16127-16130.

- [13] S. Yang, X. Feng, X. Wang, K. Müllen, Graphene-based carbon nitride nanosheets as efficient metal-free electrocatalysts for oxygen reduction reactions, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **50**, 2011, pp. 5339-5343.
- [14] J.P. Paraknowitsch, A. Thomas, Doping carbons beyond nitrogen: an overview of advanced heteroatom doped carbons with boron, sulphur and phosphorus for energy applications, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, **6**, 2013, pp. 2839-2855.
- [15] C.H. Choi, S.H. Park, S.I. Woo, Binary and ternary doping of nitrogen, boron, and phosphorus into carbon for enhancing electrochemical oxygen reduction activity, *ACS Nano*, **6**, 2012, pp. 7084-7091.
- [16] Y. Zheng, Y. Jiao, L. Ge, M. Jaroniec, S.Z. Qiao, Two-step boron and nitrogen doping in graphene for enhanced synergistic catalysis, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **125**, 2013, pp. 3192-3198.
- [17] H.W. Liang, X.D. Zhuang, S. Brüller, X.L. Feng, K. Müllen, Hierarchically porous carbons with optimized nitrogen doping as highly active electrocatalysts for oxygen reduction, *Nat. Commun.*, **5**, 2014, pp. 4937-4943.
- [18] L. Zeng, W. Zeng, Y. Jiang, X. Wei, W. Li, C. Yang, Y. Zhu, Y. Yu, A flexible porous carbon nanofibers-selenium cathode with superior electrochemical performance for both Li-Se and Na-Se batteries, *Adv. Energy Mater.*, doi: 10.1002/aenm.201401377.
- [19] P.S. Kumar, J. Sundaramurthy, S. Subramanian, V.J. Babu, G. Singh, S.I. Allakhverdiev, S. Ramakrishna, Hierarchical electrospun nanofibers for energy harvesting, production and environmental remediation, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, **7**, 2014, pp. 3192-3222.
- [20] M. Inagaki, Y. Yang, F.Y. Kang, Carbon nanofibers prepared via electrospinning, *Adv. Mater.*, **24**, 2012, pp. 2547-2566.
- [21] Z.Y. Li, H.N. Zhang, W. Zheng, W. Wang, H.M. Huang, C. Wang, A.G. MacDiarmid, Y. Wei, Highly sensitive and stable humidity nanosensors based on LiCl doped TiO₂ electrospun nanofibers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **130**, 2008, pp. 5036-5037.
- [22] C.L. Zhang, S.H. Yu, Nanoparticles meet electrospinning: recent advances and future prospects, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, **43**, 2014, pp. 4423-4448.
- [23] L.J. Li, A. Manthiram, O- and N-doped carbon nanowebs as metal-free catalysts for hybrid Li-air batteries, *Adv. Energy Mater.*, **4**, 2014, pp. 1301795-1301801.
- [24] B. Wang, Y.D. Wang, Y.P. Lei, N. Wu, Y.Z. Gou, C. Han, D. Fang, Hierarchically porous SiC ultrathin fibers mat with enhanced mass transport, amphiphatic property and high-temperature erosion resistance, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, **2**, 2014, pp. 20873-20881.
- [25] C. Han, Y.D. Wang, Y.P. Lei, B. Wang, N. Wu, Q. Shi, Q. Li, In situ synthesis of graphitic-C₃N₄ nanosheet hybridized N-doped TiO₂ nanofibers for efficient photocatalytic H₂ production and degradation, *Nano Res.*, doi: 10.1007/s12274-014-0600-2.
- [26] N. Wu, Y.D. Wang, Y.P. Lei, B. Wang, C. Han, Flexible N-doped TiO₂/C ultrafine fiber mat and its photocatalytic activity under simulated sunlight, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, **319**, 2014, pp. 136-142.
- [27] Y.D. Wang, C. Han, D.C. Zheng, Y.P. Lei, Large-scale, flexible and high-temperature resistant ZrO₂/SiC ultrafine fibers with a radial gradient composition, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, **2**, 2014, pp. 9607-9612.
- [28] K. Raidongia, A. Nag, K. Hembram, U.V. Waghmare, R. Datta, C. Rao, BCN: a graphene analogue with remarkable adsorptive properties, *Chem. Eur. J.*, **16**, 2010, pp. 149-157.
- [29] Y. Kang, Z.Y. Chu, D.J. Zhang, G.Y. Li, Z.H. Jiang, H.F. Cheng, X.D. Li, Incorporate boron and nitrogen into graphene to make BCN hybrid nanosheets with enhanced microwave absorbing properties, *Carbon*, **61**, 2013, pp. 200-208.
- [30] Y.P. Lei, Y.D. Wang, Y.C. Song, Boron nitride by pyrolysis of the melt-processable poly[tris(methylamino)borane]: structure, composition and oxidation resistance, *Ceram. Int.*, **38**, 2012, pp. 271-276.

- [31] Y.P. Lei, Y.D. Wang, J.G. Xue, Y.C. Song, Influence of pyrolysis conditions on fabrication of polymer-derived BN fiber for wave transparent application, *Compos. Part B-Eng.*, **51**, 2013, pp. 254-259.
- [32] Y.P. Lei, Y.D. Wang, Y.C. Song, Y.H. Li, C. Deng, H. Wang, Z.F. Xie, Nearly stoichiometric BN fiber with low dielectric constant derived from poly[(alkylamino)borazine], *Mater. Lett.*, **65**, 2011, pp. 157-159.
- [33] T. Kida, K. Shigezumi, M.A. Mannan, M. Akiyama, Y. Baba, M. Nagano, Synthesis of boron carbonitride (BCN) films by plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition using trimethylamine borane as a molecular precursor, *Vacuum*, **83**, 2009, pp. 1143-1146.
- [34] Y.P. Lei, Y.D. Wang, Y.C. Song, Atmosphere influence in the pyrolysis of poly[(alkylamino)borazine] for the production of BN fibers, *Ceram. Int.*, **39**, 2013, pp. 6847-6851.
- [35] Y.P. Lei, Y.D. Wang, Y.C. Song, H. Wang, Z.F. Xie, C. Deng, Effect of molecular monomer structure on the composition and properties of BN via the preceramic polymer route, *Mater. Lett.*, **65**, 2011, pp. 1111-1113.
- [36] J.I. Ozaki, N. Kimura, T. Anahar, A. Oya, Preparation and oxygen reduction activity of BN-doped carbons, *Carbon*, **45**, 2007, pp. 1847-1853.
- [37] H.L. Jiang, Y.H. Zhu, Q. Feng, Y.H. Su, X.L. Yang, C.Z. Li, Nitrogen and phosphorus dual-doped hierarchical porous carbon foams as efficient metal-free electrocatalysts for oxygen reduction reactions, *Chem. Eur. J.*, **20**, 2014, pp. 3106-3112.
- [38] P.H. Matter, U.S. Ozkan, Non-metal catalysts for dioxygen reduction in an acidic electrolyte, *Catal. Lett.*, **109**, 2006, pp.115-123.
- [39] G. Liu, X. Li, P. Ganesan, B.N. Popov, Development of non-precious metal oxygen-reduction catalysts for PEM fuel cells based on N-doped ordered porous carbon, *Appl. Catal. B: Environ.*, **93**, 2009, pp. 156-165.
- [40] B. Zhang, Z. Wen, S. Ci, S. Mao, J. Chen, Z. He, Synthesizing nitrogen-doped activated carbon and probing its active sites for oxygen reduction reaction in microbial fuel cells, *ACS Appl. Mater. Inter.*, **6**, 2014, pp. 7464-7470.
- [41] J.I. Ozaki, T. Anahara, N. Kimura, A. Oya, Simultaneous doping of boron and nitrogen into a carbon to enhance its oxygen reduction activity in proton exchange membrane fuel cells, *Carbon*, **44**, 2006, pp. 3358-3361.
- [42] J. Xu, Y. Zhao, C. Shen, L. Guan, Sulfur-and nitrogen-doped, ferrocene-derived mesoporous carbons with efficient electrochemical reduction of oxygen, *ACS Appl. Mater. Inter.*, **5**, 2013, pp. 12594-12601.
- [43] L.H. Chen, X.Y. Li, G. Tian, Y. Li, H.Y. Tan, G. Tendeloo, G. Zhu, S. Qiu, X.Y. Yang, B.L. Su, Multimodal zeolite-beta-based catalysts with a hierarchical, three-level pore structure, *ChemSusChem*, **4**, 2011, pp. 1452-1456.
- [44] R.X. Chen, J.G. Yu, W. Xiao, Hierarchically porous MnO₂ microspheres with enhanced adsorption performance, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, **1**, 2013, pp. 11682-11690.
- [45] D. Portehault, C. Giordano, C. Gervais, I. Senkowska, S. Kaskel, C. Sanchez, M. Antonietti, High-surface-area nanoporous boron carbon nitrides for hydrogen storage, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **20**, 2010, pp.1827-1833.
- [46] L.T. Qu, Y. Liu, J.B. Baek, L.M. Dai, Nitrogen-doped graphene as efficient metal-free electrocatalyst for oxygen reduction in fuel cells, *ACS Nano*, **4**, 2010, pp. 1321-1326.
- [47] J. Liang, Y. Zheng, J. Chen, J. Liu, D. Hulicova-Jurcakova, M. Jaroniec, S.Z. Qiao, Facile oxygen reduction on a three-dimensionally ordered macroporous graphitic C₃N₄/carbon composite electrocatalyst, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **51**, 2012, pp. 3892-3896.
- [48] J.F. Wu, X.Z. Yuan, J.J. Martin, H.J. Wang, J.J. Zhang, J. Shen, S.H. Wu, W. Merida, A review of PEM fuel cell durability: degradation mechanisms and mitigation strategies, *J. Power. Sources*, **184**, 2008, pp. 104-119.